

AN INTRODUCTORY REVIEW OF VEHICULAR AIR POLLUTION IN INDIA

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INTRODUCTION

Air is the ocean we breathe. Air supplies us with *oxygen* which is essential for our bodies to live. Air is 99.9% nitrogen, oxygen, water vapor and inert gases. Human activities can release substances into the air, some of which can cause problems for humans, plants, and animals. Air pollution has been aggravated by developments that typically occur as countries become industrialized: growing cities, increasing traffic, rapid economic development and industrialization, and higher levels of energy consumption. The high influxes of population to urban areas, increase in consumption patterns and unplanned urban and industrial development have led to the problem of air pollution. Currently, in India, air pollution is widespread in urban areas where vehicles are the major contributors and in a few other areas with a high concentration of industries and thermal power plants. Vehicular emissions are of particular concern since these are ground level sources and thus have the maximum impact on the general population. Also, vehicles contribute significantly to the total air pollution load in many urban areas.

VEHICULAR POLLUTION CONTROL

The Ministry plays a coordinating role in the field of controlling of vehicular pollution

Methane (CH₄)	0.22	0.35	0.39	0.91	0.17
Nitrous Oxide (N₂O)	0.54	0.54	2.98	0.54	0.54
Nitrogen Oxide (NOx)	1.06	1.45	2.33	0.97	0.92
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	0.99	0.98	0.78	0.97	0.96
Total	10.71	12.02	13.88	9.03	8.61

2. HARMFUL EFFECTS OF THE POLLUTANTS IN AIR

The various categories of air pollutants and their harmful effects are summarised in the given table:

Pollutant	Source/Cause	Effect
Carbon monoxide	Automobile exhaust,	Affects the respiratory activity as hemoglobin

	<p>photochemical reactions in the atmosphere, biological oxidation by marine organisms, etc.</p>	<p>has more affinity for Co than for oxygen. Thus, CO combines with HB and thus reduces the oxygen-carrying capacity of blood. This results in blurred vision, headache, unconsciousness and death due to asphyxiation (lack of oxygen).</p>
Carbon di oxide	<p>Carbon Burning of fossil fuels, depletion of forests (that remove excess carbon dioxide and help in maintaining the oxygen-carbon dioxide ratio).</p>	<p>Global warming as it is one of the greenhouse gases.</p>
Sulphur dioxide	<p>Industries, burning of fossil fuels, forest fires, electric generation plants, smelting plants, industrial boilers, petroleum refineries and</p>	<p>Respiratory problems, severe headache, reduced productivity of plants, yellowing and reduced storage time for paper, yellowing and damage to limestone and marble, damage to leather, increased rate of corrosion</p>

	volcanic eruptions.	of iron, steel, zinc and aluminum.
Hydrocarbons Polynuclear Aromatic Compounds(PAC) and Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons(PAH)	Automobile exhaust and industries, leaking fuel tanks, leaching from toxic waste dumping sites and coal tar lining of some water supply pipes.	Carcinogenic (may cause leukemia)
Chlorofluoro carbons (CFCs)	Refrigerators, air conditioners, foam shaving cream, spray cans and cleaning solvents.	Destroy ozone layer which then permits harmful UV rays to enter the atmosphere.
Nitrogen Oxides	Automobile exhausts, burning of fossil fuels, forest fires, electric generation plants, smelting plants, industrial boilers, petroleum refineries and volcanic eruptions	Forms photochemical smog, at higher concentrations causes leaf damage or affects the photosynthetic activities of plants and causes respiratory problems in mammals.

PAN - peroxyacetyl -nitrate	Photochemical reactions of hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides.	Irritation of eye, throat and respiratory tract, damage to clothes, paint and rubber articles, damage to leaves and stomatal tissue in plants.
Particulate matter Lead halides (lead pollution)	Combustion of leaded gasoline products	Toxic effect in man.
Asbestos particles	Mining activities	Asbestosis - a cancerous disease of the lungs
Silicon dioxide	Stone cutting, pottery, glass manufacturing and cement industries.	Silicosis, a cancerous disease.
Biological matter like the pollen grains	Flowers	Allergy
Fungal spores, bacteria, virus, etc	Microbes	Infectious diseases

3. CONTROL OF AIR POLLUTION

For effective control and prevention of air pollution it is important to educate people and create public awareness about the ill-effects of air pollution. The following are some methods that may be adopted to control pollution on a large scale:

Combustion

Pollutants in the form of organic gases or vapours can be burnt to convert them into water vapour and relatively less harmful products, such as carbon dioxide.

Absorption

The gaseous effluents may be made to pass through scrubbers or absorbers. These contain a suitable liquid absorbent, which removes or modifies one or more of the pollutants present in the gaseous effluents making it comparatively harmless.

Adsorption

The gaseous effluents are passed through porous solid adsorbents kept in suitable containers. The organic and inorganic constituents of the effluent gases are trapped at the interphase of the solid adsorbent. Adsorbents hold (molecules of a gas or liquid or solute) to its surface, causing a thin film to form.

Methods to Control Particulate Emissions

Particulate emissions may be controlled by using mechanical devices that generally work on the basis of the following:

Gravity

In this process, the particles settle down by gravitational force. Sudden changes in the direction of the gas flow causes the particles to separate out due to greater momentum.

Fabric Filters

The gases containing dust are passed through a porous medium. Which are usually woven fabrics? The particles present in the gas are trapped and collected in the filters. The gases freed from the particles are then discharged.

A Typical Bag Filter

Wet Scrubbers

Wet scrubbers are used in chemical, mining and metallurgical industries to trap sulphur dioxide, ammonia, metal fumes, etc.

Electrostatic Precipitators

When a gas or an air stream containing aerosols in the form of dust, fumes or mist, is passed between two electrodes, then, the aerosol particles get precipitated on the electrode.

Electrostatic Precipitator

The following practices also help in controlling air pollution:

- Better designed equipment and smokeless fuels must be used in hearths in industries and at home.
- Automobiles should be properly maintained and must adhere to emission - control standards. (Bharat II or Euro II)
- More trees should be planted along road-side.
- Renewable energy sources, such as wind, solar energy, ocean currents, must be tapped to fulfill energy needs.
- Tall chimneys should be installed for vertical dispersion of pollutants.

CO-BENEFITS ANALYSIS OF AIR POLLUTION AND GHG EMISSIONS

A co-benefits approach as outlined in figure below is increasingly becoming a starting point for discussing integrated programs benefiting climate change and air quality alike. Figure depicts a scenario where the co-benefits can aid decision making over a variety of control measures. For example, policies designed to reduce the impact of transport on air quality by tackling congestion and encouraging a shift to public

transport, walking, and cycling should also reduce CO₂ emissions. Measures to improve energy efficiency and cut energy demand, reduces air pollutants and GHG emissions together during electricity generation. In the developing countries, this approach is being recognized as a practical and effective tool in technical, policy, economic, and institutional perspectives.

Source: Dr. Cornie Huizenga, Executive Director, C-AI-Asia, Manila, Philippines

POLLUTION FACTS

- According to research conducted by the World Health Organization, around 2.4 million people die every year because of air pollution.
- In India, air pollution is believed to cause 527,700 fatalities a year.
- Engine exhaust (diesel and gas) contains more than 40 hazardous air pollutants.
- Traffic areas around schools - where vehicles are often left idling - show significantly higher pollution levels outside (and inside) their buildings.

surprisingly lower than the emission and violations in residential areas of India

- Vapi in Gujarat and Sukinda in Orrisa is among the world's top 10 most polluted places, according to the Blacksmith Institute, a New York-based nonprofit group.
- Air pollution caused by the burning of fossil fuels like coal and diesel has contributed to a worrisome slowdown in rice harvest growth in India in the past two decades.
- India has been ranked as the seventh most environmentally hazardous country in the world by a new ranking released recently. The study is based on evaluation of "absolute" environment impact of 179 countries, whose data was available and has been done by researchers in Harvard, Princeton, Adelaide University and University of Singapore on January 12, 2011.
- Of the four major Indian cities, air pollution was consistently worst in Delhi, every year over 5 year period (2004–2008). Kolkata was a close second, followed by Mumbai. Chennai air pollution was least of the four.
- Vehicle emissions are responsible for 70% of the country's air pollution. The major problem with government efforts to safeguard the environment has been enforcement at the local level.
- Air pollution from vehicle exhausts and industries is a worsening problem for India. Exhaust emissions from vehicles has increased eight-fold over levels of twenty years ago; industrial pollution has risen four times over the same period. The economy has grown two and a half times over the past two decades, but pollution control and civil services have not kept pace. Air quality is the worst in big cities like Kolkata, Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, etc.

air pollutants and ozone, and the latter has a harmful impact on health and agricultural yield. TERI found that cities like Delhi and Ghaziabad violate annual ambient air quality standards for particulate matter concentrations.

- Indoor air pollution: Indoor air pollution is the most important cause of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in India, says a prevalence study conducted by Pune based Chest Research Foundation (CRF) and the Imperial College, London in November 2010. Over 700 million people in India suffer from high levels of indoor air pollution affecting women and young children as 75 per cent homes use biomass fuel like wood, crop residue and dung cakes.
- The National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) is working to understand how exposure to environmental agents trigger diseases such as Asthma, and how these diseases can be prevented, diagnosed and treated.
- Municipal solid waste: With India's urban population slated to increase from the current 330 million to about 600 million by 2030, the challenge of managing municipal solid waste (MSW) in an environmentally and economically sustainable manner is bound to assume gigantic proportions. The country has over 5,000 cities and towns, which generate about 40 million tonnes of MSW per year today. Going by estimates of The Energy Research Institute (TERI), this could well touch 260 million tones per year by 2047.
- Taking a cue from the finding, the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) formulated NAAQS and checked the air quality, which led to the revelation about air quality in leading cities.

- According to the report, Gobindgarh in Punjab is the most polluted city, and Ludhiana, Raipur and Lucknow hold the next three positions. Faridabad on the outskirts of Delhi is the 10th most polluted city, followed by Agra, the city of the Taj Mahal. Ahmedabad is placed 12th, Indore 16th, Delhi 22nd, Kolkata 25th, Mumbai 40th, Hyderabad 44th and Bangalore stands at 46th in the list. The Orissa town of Angul, home to National Aluminium Company (NALCO), is the 50th polluted city of the country.

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